

Multiphase Analysis of Water Atomisation using VOF in a Pneumatic Spray Nozzle by Varying the Atomiser Plate Geometry

C. Kringel^a, V. Mølbak^a

^aAalborg University, Faculty of Engineering and Science, Niels Jernes Vej 12, DK-9220 Aalborg East, Denmark

Abstract

Spray nozzles for pesticide spraying in unmanned drones have in recent years increased in interest. In this application, achieving a consistent droplet size from the nozzle is essential to achieve the desired dispersion of pesticides. This study will analyse the effect of geometric changes within a pneumatic nozzle, to understand how geometric parameters impact the droplet size, by applying a multiphase CFD model using the Eulerian VoF approach for $Re = 20,000$. The atomiser plate geometry within the nozzle is changed by applying a staircase like structure, with various number of steps with different step angles θ . An analysis is then carried out on how the water separation occurs on the plate, and thus impacts the droplet distribution. It is concluded, that introducing the staircase structure will, in general, result in a more consistent droplet size distribution. Additionally, the cases with fewest steps and steepest step angle, decreases the amount of large droplets formed by the nozzle by 15% and 27%, respectively. Based on the water film analysis, this occurs since droplets are more likely to separate before the trailing edge, as the step angle and step count decreases. The paper illustrates, that the atomiser plate significantly impacts the size of droplets formed in a pneumatic nozzle.

Keywords: Multiphase, CFD, LES, OpenFOAM, Volume of Fluid, isoAdvector, Pneumatic Nozzle

1. Introduction

Spray nozzles have in recent years been studied for various industrial applications such as pesticide spraying within the agricultural industry. More specifically, is the use of spray nozzles attached to unmanned drones for pesticide spraying operations (Ni et al., 2021) (Hong et al., 2018). For this application, droplets that are too small might drift away before reaching the ground below, not applying the desired amount of pesticide (Chen et al., 2020). However, droplets that are too large could damage the ground or plants below and also provide an unnecessarily large amount of pesticide which could be harmful to the environment (Mahmood et al., 2015). Research into how a nozzle could be designed, as to achieve a consistent droplet size is thus of interest.

Studies on the effect of changing the geometric parameters of a pneumatic nozzle has, been done by Alidoost Dafsari et al. (2021) and Meakhail et al. (2008), who found that changes in geometric parameters can have a noticeable effect on droplet spread and size. Both of these analyses were however performed experimentally, why research using a numerical analysis on the effect of changes of the nozzle geometry is lacking. The inlet air pressure in a

pneumatic nozzle was studied by Jiang et al. (2022) and Sapee (2015), who found that it has a considerable impact on droplet diameter, where an increase in air pressure would result in a decrease in droplet diameters.

To perform the analysis of the geometry changes within the nozzle numerically, a Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) analysis will be done. To model the multiphase behaviour of the atomisation within the nozzle, there are generally two methods, the Eulerian and Lagrangian approach. In the Lagrangian approach, the droplets are considered as a dispersed phase, and their trajectory is tracked individually. For the Eulerian approach, the particle and fluid are treated as a continuum, and the equations are solved in a control volume. A commonly used subset of the Eulerian approach is the Volume of Fluid (VoF) method, where the interface between different phases are tracked throughout a computational grid (Hirt and Nichols, 1981).

A comparison between the two approaches was done by Xu et al. (2020), where the authors analysed liquid droplets within gaseous domains both numerically and experimentally. They found that the Eulerian method performed better than the Lagrangian method in terms of accuracy and computational time. Zhang and Chen (2007) performed the same comparison and found that the two approaches were comparable in terms of results, however the Eulerian approach was superior in terms of computational time.

The VoF method, used in Zhao et al. (2022) and Arcoumanis et al. (1999), showed promising results for the

^{*}This manuscript is submitted for the CES student conference organised by Department of Energy Technology, Aalborg University.

^{*}Corresponding author:

Email addresses: ckring19@student.aau.dk (C. Kringel),
vmalba19@student.aau.dk (V. Mølbak)

(a) The computational domain seen in the yz -plane, excluding the diverging section.

(b) The computational domain seen in the xy -plane.

Figure 1: The computational domain. The atomiser plate is based on a NACA0015 airfoil.

Table 1: Dimensions of the computational domain. Note that, the width of the computational domain, L_1 , is based on the integral length scale, defined by a two-point correlation shown in Section 3.7.

Symbol	L_1	d	L_3	L_4	L_5	L_6	L_7	L_8
Value	$0.7D$	$D/15$	$1.5D$	$2.5D$	$1.5D$	$3D/10$	$2D$	$2D$

general case of liquid in gas, when comparing results of a VoF CFD model with experimental results. Additionally, the VoF method is often used in relation with Unsteady Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (URANS) turbulence modelling, however Malvin et al. (2014) modelled multiphase flow using VoF and employed Large Eddy Simulation (LES) turbulence modelling. They found that, for the specific case, the model resulted in errors of just 3% to 10% when comparing with experimental data.

This study will investigate a pneumatic air-water nozzle design in an effort to reduce the amount of large droplets exiting the nozzle and thereby achieve a more consistent droplet size. The droplet formation within the nozzle will be modelled numerically by the Eulerian VoF approach using LES turbulence modelling.

This study first presents the computational domain and geometry, before describing the numerical framework on which the CFD model is constructed. Results are then presented for droplet distribution and- formation when varying the nozzle geometry. Finally, the water film along the airfoil is analysed for the different geometries.

2. Geometry and Computational Domain

The geometry of the pneumatic nozzle is seen in Figure 1 with associated parameters listed in Table 1. The geometry of the atomiser plate in the nozzle is a NACA0015 airfoil.

The water inlet is placed at the airfoil leading edge, with water exiting the inlet in the negative x -direction, while air flows in the positive x -direction.

The diverging section of the geometry can be described by the sinusoidal curve

$$f(x) = \frac{D}{4} \sin \left(x \frac{3}{14.325} - \frac{\pi}{2} \right) + \frac{D}{4} \quad 0 \leq x \leq D \quad (1)$$

To greatly reduce the computational domain, periodic boundary conditions have been employed for the boundaries normal to the xy -plane, as seen in Figure 1a. The computational domain thus simulates a small part of the total nozzle width with a single water inlet.

Changes are made on the airfoil to create a staircase geometry from the point of maximum thickness to the trailing edge of the airfoil. The geometry of the staircase is varied using the parameters, staircase step count (SC) and the step angle θ . Figure 2 presents how these parameters affects the airfoil shape for a case of 2 steps and $\theta = 90$.

The length and shape of the leading edge to the point of maximum airfoil thickness, L_{11} , is kept constant throughout the analysis. The step depth, L_9 , and step length, L_{10} , are functions that depend on the geometric parameters, and can be seen in Table 2 and Equation 2.

Figure 2: Parametric airfoil geometry. The presented airfoil is for a case of 2 steps and $\theta = 90$.

Table 2: Parameters describing various airfoil lengths.

Symbol	L_9	L_{10}	L_{11}
Value	$L_6/2SC$	(2)	$0.6D$

$$L_{10} = \frac{L_7 - L_{11}}{SC} + \frac{\cos \theta L_9}{\sin \theta} \quad (2)$$

3. Numerical Framework and Method

In this paper, the VoF method is used to track the interface between water and air as the primary and secondary phase, respectively. The interface is tracked with the step function α , which marks the volume fraction of a tracked phase in a control volume. This means that $\alpha = 1$ is a control volume occupied purely by water and $\alpha = 0$ is a control volume that contains no water; therefore, only air is present. The interface is represented by control volumes where $0 < \alpha < 1$.

The use of α allows the need for only a single set of equations to calculate the properties of the phases locally, since α can be used as a weight. The density in the domain can therefore be calculated as

$$\rho = \alpha \rho_{\text{water}} + (1 - \alpha) \rho_{\text{air}} \quad (3)$$

and similarly for the dynamic viscosity.

3.1. Governing Equations

The VoF model solves the Navier-Stokes equations for a flow of two incompressible, isothermal and immiscible fluids. The continuity equation for the mass in a control volume is then

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla(\rho \mathbf{u}) = 0 \quad (4)$$

where the fluid velocity is represented by \mathbf{u} . The momentum equation is expressed as

$$\frac{\partial(\rho \mathbf{u})}{\partial t} + \nabla(\rho \mathbf{u} \mathbf{u}) = -\nabla p + \nabla \mathbf{T} + \rho \mathbf{g} + F_\sigma \quad (5)$$

where p is the pressure, \mathbf{T} is the stress tensor, \mathbf{g} is the body forces, which in this case is simply gravity, and F_σ represents the surface tension (Gopala and van Wachem, 2008).

An additional equation is solved for the interface between the two fluids, the advection equation, as to describe the transport of the volume fraction α

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} + \nabla(\alpha \mathbf{u}) = 0 \quad (6)$$

To model the stresses caused by eddies in the subgrid-scale which is not captured by LES, the subgrid-scale model Wall Adapting Local Eddy-viscosity is used. This model is particularly suited for wall-bounded flow, since the eddy-viscosity naturally approaches zero near the wall (Nicoud and Ducros, 1999).

3.2. Water Interface Representation

In the VoF method, the volume fraction α represents the average value within a cell in the computational domain, why information about the interface between liquid and gas is not easily available, especially in cases where the interfaces cuts through a cell. Tracking this interface is therefore essential to the success of the VoF method. There are generally two methods for interface capturing, the *geometric* and *algebraic* schemes.

For algebraic schemes (Darwish and Moukalled, 2006; Heyns et al., 2013; Deshpande et al., 2012), the volume fraction is directly interpolated at the surface from the volume fraction within a given cell with high order difference schemes. However, this can result in numerical diffusion, smearing the interface (Comminal and Spangenberg, 2021).

By comparison, the geometric schemes approximate the volume fraction by reconstructing the interface according to the volume fraction within the computational cell. The most commonly used reconstruction method is Piecewise Linear Interface Calculations presented by Rider and Kothe (1998), which represents the volume fraction inside the cell by a planar surface.

Roenby et al. (2016) proposed the isoAdvector geometric scheme for unstructured meshes. This scheme finds the isosurface inside a cell that accurately splits the cell according to the interface volume fraction. Thereby allowing for a more accurate calculation of face fluxes. Roenby et al. (2016) also compares the isoAdvector scheme with three algebraic VoF schemes and finds that it outperforms all schemes for both unstructured and structured meshes, and for a range of Courant numbers.

In general, geometric schemes are preferred to algebraic schemes for interface tracking. Additionally, the isoAdvector scheme is shown to perform well and is easily implemented in the numerical software used in this paper, why it will be employed for the analysis. A more thorough review of interface tracking schemes is presented in Marić et al. (2020).

3.3. Dimensionless Parameters

Air enters the computational domain with bulk velocity U_b , giving a Reynolds number of

$$\text{Re} = \frac{U_b D}{\nu} = 20,000 \quad (7)$$

The Reynolds number is based on the height of the computational domain, D .

Water exits the nozzle at the leading edge of the airfoil at a constant rate of $\frac{U_w}{U_b} = 0.025$, where U_w is the water velocity.

The droplet size throughout the paper will be represented using the dimensionless Weber number defined as

$$\text{We} = \frac{\rho_{\text{water}} U_b d_{\text{droplet}}}{\sigma} \quad (8)$$

where σ is the surface tension at ambient temperature, and d_{droplet} is the droplet diameter.

3.4. Boundary Conditions and Simulation Parameters

For the air, a fully developed turbulent velocity profile has been applied at the inlet boundary with bulk velocity U_b . The boundary condition is set using the Divergence Free Synthetic Eddy Method (DFSEM). Poletto et al. (2013) showed that DFSEM results in a maximum error of just 4% in the wall-skin friction, C_f , compared with periodic LES results, and a vast improvement over similar methods for the generation of synthetic turbulence such as Synthetic Eddies Method (SEM).

The water inlet boundary condition is set as a fully developed laminar velocity profile, and a constant contact angle between the water and the walls and airfoil is set to $\beta = 75^\circ$.

For stability, the Courant-Friedrichs-Levy (CFL) condition, which decides the time step, is set as $CFL = U \Delta t / \Delta x < 0.95$.

3.5. Data Visualisation Using a Probability Density Function

To comprehensibly visualise the histogram of the droplet size distribution, a probability density function (PDF) is fitted to the histogram data. Conde-Fontenla et al. (2021) studied the fitting of different PDFs for droplet distributions, which showed that the inverse Gaussian and lognormal PDFs deviated up to 3% from the experimental results. The lognormal PDF was chosen for this study because it is widely used within the field of droplet distribution, while still being able to present an accurate fitting, as supported by the work of Martandez-Cuenca et al. (2015) and Pano (2023).

3.6. Mesh Independence

To ensure results independent of mesh refinement, a mesh independence analysis is done. The droplet size distribution has been obtained for three different mesh refinements. A coarse mesh with 550,000 cells, medium mesh with 1,070,000 cells and a fine mesh with 2,130,000 cells. The analysis showed that the fine mesh obtained results independent of refinement.

The mesh is seen in Figure 3 in the xy -plane and two slices in the yz -plane along the flow direction, to illustrate how the refinement region initially is a square before becoming a cone further downstream of the airfoil. Additionally, the mesh is graded in the y -direction to more accurately refine the boundary region at the walls.

3.7. Two-Point Correlation Determining Computational Domain Width

The width of the computational domain will be based on the integral length scale as to ensure that a minimum of the large eddies cross the cyclic boundaries. The integral length scale is estimated by a two-point correlation, as described in Davidson (2022), where velocity fluctuations v'_1 are sampled throughout the domain. The normalised

Figure 3: Illustration of the mesh used for simulations. Shown in the xy -plane and yz -plane.

correlation $B_{11}^{\text{norm}}(\hat{x}_1)$ can then be set up, and the integral length scale to evaluate the size of the large energy-containing eddies is defined as

$$L_{\text{int}} = \int_0^\infty B_{11}^{\text{norm}}(\hat{x}_1) d\hat{x}_1 \quad (9)$$

In this way, the point where no correlation occurs, thereby giving the integral length scale, is found at $B^{\text{norm}} = 0$. The instantaneous velocity is sampled at three different points throughout the geometry to ensure that the effect of a range of eddies, is captured. The two-point correlation for the three samples can be seen in Figure 4.

The Figure shows that, for all three samples, no correlation occurs between the first point and subsequent points at a distance of approximately $0.7D$. The integral length scale, and the width of the computational domain is thereby defined as such.

Figure 4: Two-point correlation for the instantaneous velocity. Line 1 refers to a sample taken above the airfoil, while Line 2 and 3 refers to samples up- and downstream of the airfoil respectively.

4. Results and Discussion

The airfoil will be varied according to Figure 2, where step count and step angle, will be varied to create nine different airfoil geometries. The nine cases are presented in Table 3. To act as a baseline value for comparison, the results of the NACA0015 airfoil presented in the computational domain in Figure 1b, will be used.

	Step count	θ
Case 1	2	90
Case 2	4	90
Case 3	6	90
Case 4	8	90
Case 5	10	90
Case 6	4	50
Case 7	4	70
Case 8	4	110
Case 9	4	130

Table 3: The nine different cases which are investigated in the parametric study.

The cases will be compared in terms of the droplet lognormal distribution and the cumulative density function (CDF) to analyse how the different airfoil geometries impact the size of droplets formed in the nozzle. As it is essential in most pesticide spray applications to achieve a consistent droplet size of very fine to fine droplets, the amount of coarse droplets, as classified by the American Society of Agricultural and Biological Engineers (ASABE, 2023), will be considered. Coarse droplets corresponds to a Weber number of $We > 1900$ and will be defined by the fraction

$$\zeta = \frac{n_{We>1900}}{n_{tot}} \quad (10)$$

where n_{tot} is the total number of droplets formed for a given airfoil geometry.

Finally, the water film along the airfoil for each case will be presented to compare how the different step configurations impact the point at which water separation occurs along the airfoil.

4.1. Influence of Step Count on Droplet Distribution

Figure 5 shows the lognormal distribution in Figure 5a and CDF in Figure 5b for Cases 1, 2, and 5 with varying step count. The baseline results are also presented for comparison.

Figure 5a shows, that changing the airfoil by adding steps will, in general, narrow the droplet distribution compared with the baseline airfoil, as this behaviour is observed for all cases presented. Additionally, the Figure show similar droplet distributions with varying step count, with fewer steps resulting in a slightly more concentrated distribution, peaking at a step count of 2.

The same tendencies are seen in Figure 5b, where Case 1 with 2 steps result in the steepest CDF indicating a

more consistent droplet size for this case. Additionally, the difference between each case is more pronounced in the CDF analysis.

4.1.1. Fraction of Large Droplets for Step Count Variation

Figure 6a shows how varying the step count above 4 has a negligible effect of the amount of large droplets. However, at a step count of 2, a big decrease in large droplets is seen, resulting in a 15% improvement compared with the baseline. This could possibly be due to the fact, that fewer steps result in a larger step height, L_6 , per step, which could increase the probability of droplets separating at the steps. This also indicates, that a break point for which the water film separates along the airfoil, is reached at a step count of 2 or below. It is also seen that all step counts above 2 result in a larger fraction of large droplets compared to the baseline, hence an improvement upon the baseline airfoil only occurs for low step counts.

4.2. Influence of Step Angle on Droplet Distribution

Figure 5 shows the lognormal distribution in Figure 5c and CDF in Figure 5d for Case 2, 6 and 9 with varying step angle θ on the airfoil. The baseline results are also presented for comparison.

Figure 5c indicates, that a step angle of $\theta < 90$ will result in a larger concentration of droplets at a Weber number of roughly $We = 600$ compared to more obtuse angles. Comparing with the Baseline distribution, all cases presented also result in a more narrow distribution.

Considering the CDF for each case in Figure 5d, the case with a step angle of $\theta = 50$ shows clear improvements in the steepness of the CDF, indicating a very consistent droplet size. The baseline CDF also seems to outperform the additional two cases of $\theta = 90$ and $\theta = 130$ in terms of large droplets, as the 90th percentile is reached at a lower Weber number.

4.2.1. Fraction of Large Droplets for Step Angle Variation

Figure 6b shows a strong positive correlation between all step angles tested and the fraction of large droplets. Furthermore, for cases with a step angle below $\theta = 90$, fewer large droplets are produced compared to the baseline. For $\theta = 50$ and $\theta = 70$ a 27% and 17% decrease is found respectively, when compared with the baseline. This could be because the droplets are more likely to separate from the airfoil at the steps with a steeper angle, reducing the overall amount of water separating at the trailing edge of the airfoil, thus resulting in smaller droplets being formed. Comparing the results with the analysis of step count, the step angle seems to have a larger effect, when reducing the fraction of large droplets is of interest.

4.3. Water Film Separation on Varying Airfoil Geometries

Figure 7 shows how the water film running along the airfoil separates for several airfoil geometries. Figures 7a

(a) Lognormal distribution for varying step count.

(b) CDF for varying step count.

(c) Lognormal distribution for varying step angle θ .

(d) CDF for varying step angle θ .

Figure 5: Results of the lognormal distribution in (a) and (c) and CDF in (b) and (d) with varying step count and step angle. Baseline describes a NACA0015 airfoil. A constant step angle of $\theta = 90$ has been used for the analysis of step count, and a constant step count of 4 has been used for the analysis of step angle. The y -axis has been normalised with the total droplet count in the droplet distributions.

to 7c shows the step count variation while Figures 7d to 7f shows the step angle variation. The Figure supports the hypothesis from the previous analysis of droplet distribution and fraction of large droplets, that larger steps and steeper angles causes parts of the water film to separate at the steps. This results in less total water separating at the trailing edge of the airfoil, thus meaning smaller droplets being formed. The figure also shows, that as more steps are introduced and the angle increases, the geometry tends towards a smooth airfoil, therefore the water film is less likely to separate.

5. Conclusion

The water atomisation process in a pneumatic air-water nozzle design is resolved using numerical Large-Eddy Simulations for various atomiser plate designs. Nine different designs are tested, taking offset in a NACA0015 airfoil with a staircase feature implemented from the point

of maximum thickness to the trailing edge. By varying the staircase step count and the step angle, θ , of the staircase feature, droplet size distribution and the water film, are investigated.

Implementing a staircase feature is found to increase consistency of the droplet size formed, compared to a baseline NACA0015 airfoil without the staircase feature. While keeping $\theta = 90$, a decreasing step count shows an increasing droplet size consistency. The same phenomenon is found for the step angle, where, at a constant step count of 4, a decrease in the step angle results in an increase in droplet size consistency.

When analysing large droplets formed by the nozzle with a Weber number greater than 1900, three staircase designs show an improvement over the baseline. With a step count of 2 and $\theta = 90$, the amount of large droplets decreases by 15%. With a constant step count of 4 and a step angle of $\theta = 50$ and $\theta = 70$ the amount of large droplets decreases by 27% and 17%, respectively.

Figure 6: Fraction of large droplets with a Weber number of $We > 1900$ for varying step count and step angle. Baseline describes the value of a NACA0015 airfoil. A constant step angle of $\theta = 90$ and constant step count of 4 is used in (a) and (b) respectively.

Figure 7: Water film along the airfoil after a simulation time of $t^* = \frac{t U_b}{D} = 105$, for several airfoil geometries. The images shown are in the xy -plane. It should be noted, that even though the images are captured after equal simulation time, the water film snapshot for a given geometry may still vary for different times. Although the same general conclusions can likely be reached.

For the cases which does not improve upon the baseline airfoil in terms of large droplets, the water film is found to be consistent. These cases show an attached water film from the leading edge to the trailing edge of the airfoil. For the three cases with fewer large droplets than in the baseline case, partial separation occurs at each step due to larger steps and steeper step angles, resulting in a more consistent droplet size distribution and fewer large droplets.

6. Acknowledgements

The authors would like to acknowledge and thank Anna Lyhne Jensen, who contributed to this work with great inputs.

References

- Alidoost Dafsari R, Yu S, Choi Y, Lee J. Effect of geometrical parameters of air-induction nozzles on droplet characteristics and behaviour. *Biosystems Engineering* 2021;209:14–29. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1537511021001379>. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2021.06.013>.
- Arcoumanis C, Gavaises M, Argueyrolles B, Galzin F. Modeling of pressure-swirl atomizers for gdi engines. *SAE Transactions* 1999;108:516–32. URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/44743389>.
- ASABE . Asabe s572.1 droplet size classification. 2023. URL: https://cdn2.hubspot.net/hub/95784/file-32015844-pdf/docs/asabe_s572.1_droplet_size_classification.pdf.
- Chen S, Lan Y, Zhou Z, Ouyang F, Wang G, Huang X, Deng X, Cheng S. Effect of droplet size parameters on droplet deposition and drift of aerial spraying by using plant protection uav. *Agronomy* 2020;10(2). URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/2073-4395/10/2/195>. doi:10.3390/agronomy10020195.
- Comminal R, Spangenberg J. Three-dimensional cellwise conservative unsplit geometric vof schemes. *Journal of Computational Physics* 2021;442:110479. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0021999121003740>. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcp.2021.110479>.
- Conde-Fontenla M, Paz C, Concheiro M, Ribatski G. On the width and mean value of bubble size distributions under subcooled flow boiling. *Experimental Thermal and Fluid Science* 2021;124:110368. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0894177721000212>. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.expthermflusci.2021.110368>.
- Darwish M, Moukalled F. Convective schemes for capturing interfaces of free-surface flows on unstructured grids. *Numerical Heat Transfer, Part B: Fundamentals* 2006;49(1):19–42. doi:10.1080/10407790500272137.
- Davidson L. Fluid mechanics, turbulent flow and turbulence modeling. Division of Fluid Dynamics, Department of Mechanics and Maritime Sciences, Chalmers University of Technology, 2022. URL: http://www.tfd.chalmers.se/~lada/postscript_files/solids-and-fluids_turbulent-flow_turbulence-modelling.pdf.
- Deshpande SS, Anumolu L, Trujillo MF. Evaluating the performance of the two-phase flow solver interFoam. *Computational Science Discovery* 2012;URL: <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1749-4699/5/1/014016>.
- Gopala VR, van Wachem BG. Volume of fluid methods for immiscible-fluid and free-surface flows. *Chemical Engineering Journal* 2008;141(1):204–21. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1385894708000028>. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2007.12.035>.
- Heyns JA, Malan AG, Harms TM, Oxtoby OF. Development of a compressive surface capturing formulation for modelling free-surface flow by using the volume-of-fluid approach. *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Fluids* 2013;71(6):788–804. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/flid.3694>. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/flid.3694>.
- Hirt C, Nichols B. Volume of fluid (vof) method for the dynamics of free boundaries. *Journal of Computational Physics* 1981;39(1):201–25. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0021999181901455>. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-9991\(81\)90145-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-9991(81)90145-5).
- Hong SW, Zhao L, Zhu H. Cfd simulation of pesticide spray from air-assisted sprayers in an apple orchard: Tree deposition and off-target losses. *Atmospheric Environment* 2018;175:109–19. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1352231017308245>. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2017.12.001>.
- Jiang L, Rao W, Deng L, Incecik A, Królczyk G, Li Z. Measuring liquid droplet size in two-phase nozzle flow employing numerical and experimental analyses. *Micromachines* 2022;13(5). URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/2072-666X/13/5/684>. doi:10.3390/mi13050684.
- Mahmood I, Imadi S, Shazadi K, Gul A, Hakeem K. Effects of Pesticides on Environment. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-27455-3_13.
- Malvin A, Chan A, Lau PL. Cfd study of distillation sieve tray flow regimes using the droplet size distribution technique. *Journal of the Taiwan Institute of Chemical Engineers* 2014;45(4):1354–68. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1876107014000030>. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtice.2014.01.002>.
- Marić T, Kothe DB, Bothe D. Unstructured un-split geometrical volume-of-fluid methods – a review. *Journal of Computational Physics* 2020;420:109695. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0021999120304691>. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcp.2020.109695>.
- MartÁnez-Cuenca R, Brooks CS, Enrique JuliÁn J, Hibiki T, Ishii M. Stochastic Nature of Wall Nucleation and Its Impact on the Time Average Boundary Condition. *Journal of Heat Transfer* 2015;137(2):021504. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4028975>. doi:10.1115/1.4028975.
- Meakhail TA, Zien Y, Elsallak M, AbdelHady S. Experimental study of the effect of some geometric variables and number of nozzles on the performance of a subsonic air–air ejector. *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part A: Journal of Power and Energy* 2008;222(8):809–18. doi:10.1243/09576509jpe618.
- Ni M, Wang H, Liu X, Liao Y, Fu L, Wu Q, Mu J, Chen X, Li J. Design of variable spray system for plant protection uav based on cfd simulation and regression analysis. *Sensors* 2021;21(2):638. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/s21020638>. doi:10.3390/s21020638.
- Nicoud F, Ducros F. Subgrid-scale stress modelling based on the square of the velocity gradient tensor. *Flow, Turbulence and Combustion* 1999;URL: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1023/A:1009995426001>. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1009995426001>.
- Pano MRO. Why drop size distributions in sprays fit the lognormal. *Physics of Fluids* 2023;35(1):011701. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0135510>. doi:10.1063/5.0135510.
- Poletto R, Craft T, Revell A. A New Divergence Free Synthetic Eddy Method for the Reproduction of Inlet Flow Conditions for LES. *Flow Turbulence Combust*, 2013. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10494-013-9488-2>.
- Rider WJ, Kothe DB. Reconstructing volume tracking. *Journal of Computational Physics* 1998;141(2):112–52. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S002199919895906X>. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1006/jcph.1998.5906>.
- Roenby J, Bredmose H, Jasak H. A computational method for sharp interface advection. *R. Soc*, 2016. URL: <http://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.160405>.
- Sapee S. Computational fluid dynamics study on droplet size of kerosene fuel 2015;:2289–7879.
- Xu Z, Han Z, Qu H. Comparison between lagrangian and eulerian approaches for prediction of particle deposition in turbulent flows. *Powder Technology* 2020;360:141–50. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0032591019308204>. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2019.09.084>.
- Zhang Z, Chen Q. Comparison of the eulerian and lagrangian methods for predicting particle transport in enclosed spaces. *Atmospheric Environment* 2007;41(25):5236–48. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1352231007002786>. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2006.05.086>; indoor Air 2005 - 10th International Conference on Indoor Air Quality and Climate (Part II).
- Zhao Y, Wen L, Zhang Y, Liu B, Yang H, Deng Q. Experimental and numerical study on dynamic characteristics of droplet impacting on a hot tailings surface. *Processes* 2022;10(9). URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/2227-9717/10/9/1766>. doi:10.3390/pr10091766.